

ISSUES OF TEACHING SPEAKING SKILLS USING ROLE PLAYS

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Abstract. The article examines the value and benefits of using role-playing to teach speaking as a core competency in EFL classes, as well as how well it helps language learners acquire the language. Students basically develop their oral skills within role playing. One of the main issues facing teachers today is getting students to speak up, so this approach encourages students to speak up in class, develops more fluency than accuracy, and emphasizes the act of communication.

Keywords: social context, teaching method, role-play, fluency.

Аннотация. Одной из основных проблем, стоящих сегодня перед преподавателем – научить обучающихся навыкам устной связанной речи. Такой подход побуждает обучающихся высказываться, развивает точность устной речи, делает процесс усвоения презентуемого материала интересной. В исследовании обосновываются преимущества использования ролевых игр при обучении говорению как основной компетенции формируемой на занятиях.

Ключевые слова: социальный контекст, метод обучения, ролевая игра, беглость речи.

Annotatsiya. Bugungi kunda o'qituvchilar oldida turgan asosiy muammolardan biri o'quvchilarga og'zaki bog'langan nutq malakalarini o'rgatishdir. Bunday yondashuv o'quvchilarni o'z nutqlarini shakllantirishga undaydi, og'zaki nutqning aniqligini rivojlantiradi va taqdim etilgan materialni o'zlashtirish jarayonini qiziqarli qiladi. Tadqiqotda rolli o'yinlar asosida til o'rganuvchilar nutqini shakllantirish ustuvor usul ekanligi asoslab berilgan

Kalit so'zlar: ijtimoiy kontekst, o'qitish usuli, rolli o'yin, nutq ravonligi.

English emerges as the world's most vital language. It is used for communication by almost everyone in the world, regardless of nationality. The reason for this is that English is crucial in every aspect of our lives. Speaking is a language ability used in oral communication to convey concepts, emotions, options, thoughts, and information that facilitates interpersonal communication. Learning a language involves more than just memorizing syntax and vocabulary; it also entails learning how to communicate with others by speaking clearly and using appropriate body language. Additionally, in order to develop speaking activities, students require favorable conditions, such as a language-learning environment, to increase their frequency of speaking.

Using role play as a teaching tool for speaking is crucial because it allows students to practice speaking in a variety of social roles and contexts. It also gives students the chance to be imaginative and temporarily position themselves in the shoes of another person. The role play seems like the perfect exercise for encouraging students to use their English creatively. It aims to put students in conversational situations and give them a chance to practice and improve their abilities to communicate. Role-playing helps students become more fluent speakers. More so than in any other activity, the vast array of language functions—such as expressing regret and broadening greetings—are used. Instead of emphasizing the proper use of language, learners are focused on communicating meaning. As a result, teachers can help students practice speaking in a variety of social settings by employing role-playing. It implies that students are placed in situations that call for speech that is more frequently used for social communication than the language required by curricula [2, 6]. The author adopts the stance that role-playing makes it possible to acquire language that is important in social interactions but is often overlooked in educational materials.

We can take into consideration following features of role play technique in teaching speaking skills:

➤ Role play as a teaching technique has a positive effect on students' speaking as students feel self confident and speak without fear.

➤ Role play reduces anxiety and humiliation when speaking up in front of classmates and it helps the students to develop the micro and the macro skills of language.

➤ Adopting Role play as a teaching technique in the teaching and learning process of English learners encourages these students to learn, achieve, explore and simulate their creativity, imagination and personal likes.

One more benefit of role-playing is that it gives learners the opportunity to play the part of someone else. This method could assist shy students in getting over their speech phobia. Students who are reticent frequently find it difficult to talk about themselves or their experiences. They believe their own personality is unaffected because they are someone else.

Learning a foreign language is a complex and long process as anyone who has tried will agree. One of the most difficult and frustrating things is making the transition from the classroom to the 'real' world. In the classroom, everyone knows you are a student and mistakes are allowed, and the environment is contained and safe. Speaking another language outside the classroom is completely different and often students are lost at sea as soon as they step outside the door. Lists of memorized vocabulary are suddenly useless when ordering in a restaurant. According to Gillian's opinion, students or learners need some practice during the lesson. There are a lot of interaction patterns in which we can involve our learners during the lesson and one of them is applying role-plays in teaching foreign languages. Jeremy Harmer described Role Play as an activity: role play is an effective activity for adults and teenagers, because it increases learning retention, provides hands-on training, and enables better teamwork and communication. When students take part in Role Plays, they usually get lots of fun and they try to show their ability in acting as famous actors or actresses: that is a fact; we also use some drama acting during the lesson to get students' emotional abilities:

Applying role-plays has the following benefits:

- Students immediately apply content in a relevant, real-world context.
- Pupils make decisions that may allow them to grow free from the constraints of their typical boundaries or self-imposed restrictions.
- Pupils hold the ability to think and transcend beyond the boundaries of the classroom.
- Individuals might be excessively timid.
- It becomes challenging for educators to assess each student on an individual basis.
- It's a laborious procedure.
- When the group is not understanding, it is a failure.

Getting all of the students to participate and be honestly engaged in the role playing technique is one of the biggest challenges. Teachers should think concerning strategies to boost the possibility of active student participation. A participation grade that is in some way related to a brief product that students create from their perspective in their assigned role may be offered by the instructor.

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